

Effects of Palm Kernel Shells Sizes and Mix Ratios on Lightweight Concrete

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Abstract

This paper gives an account of the study conducted on the effects of Palm Kernel Shells (PKS) sizes and percentages in lightweight concrete. It is aimed at determining the properties of PKS that make it suitable for light weight concrete works and the effects of proportion of sizes and percentages on the strength characteristics of palm kernel shell concrete. A number of tests were conducted on the PKS and concrete produced with it. Tests conducted on PKS were sieve analysis, specific gravity, water absorption capacity and moisture content, while tests conducted on palm kernel shell concrete (PKSC) included slump test, compressive strength test, modulus of rupture and splitting tensile strength test. Concrete mixes of 1:1½:3, 1:2:4, 1:3:6 and 1:4:8 were used to produce cubes, beams and cylinders which were cured for 7, 14 and 28 days before testing. PKSC had density that was less than 2000 kg/m³ for a light weight concrete. The results showed that concrete mix of 1:1½:3 with compressive strength of 20.1N/mm² at 28 days hydration period met the British Standard recommended minimum strength of 15N/mm² for structural lightweight concrete while other concrete mixes did not but they can also be employed as plain concrete. Results of tests on modulus of rupture and splitting tensile strength exhibited similar trend to that of compressive strength test. The nominal mix 1:1½:3 gave the highest values of modulus of rupture and splitting tensile strength.

Keywords:

Lightweight concrete, PKS, nominal mixes, compressive strength

1. Introduction

Palm Kernel Shell was partially a waste in the 1990s and early 2000 as more than 350,000 tons were available for sale. The PKS had

been a little known then for its potential usage on a large scale especially in concrete work (Mohammad, 2007). Beyond 2000, research into utilization of Palm Kernel Shell as light weight concrete and other uses had received a big boost. Palm kernel shells (PKS) are organic waste materials obtained from crude palm oil producing factories in Asia and Africa (Alengaram, et al, 2010). The Palm Oil Plant (*Elaeis Guinensis*), considering its three different varieties Durà, Pesipherà and Tenerà, produces an edible fruit similar to an apricot which has a nut inside. During the crude palm oil process the fruit's flesh is melted through a steaming treatment. The residual nuts are further mechanically crushed to extract the seeds or kernels. The Palm Kernel Shells (PKS) is a virgin biomass with a high calorific value, typically about 3,800 Kcal/kg (ASTM, 1978). Oil Palm trees grow in the coastal belt in Nigeria which varies in depth from 100 to 150 miles and a riverine belt which follows the valleys of the Niger and Benue for a distance of about 450 miles from the sea. The main palm oil producing states include Ogun, Ondo, Oyo, Edo, Cross River, Anambra, Enugu, Imo, Abia, Ekiti, Akwa-Ibom, Delta and Rivers.

Palm kernel shells in the past had been used solely as fuelling material at home and for industries. The quest for alternative civil engineering construction material which is economical and light in weight has been a major drive in carrying out this work. Figures 1 and 2 show a Palm Oil Plant plantation and different sizes of palm kernel shell respectively. Palm kernel shell possesses a hard characteristics as coarse aggregate and there have been attempts to use it as a coarse aggregate to replace conventional coarse aggregates traditionally used for concrete production (Mohd et al., 2008). Ata et al (2006) compared the mechanical properties of palm kernel shell concrete with that of coconut shell concrete and reported the economy of using palm kernel shell as lightweight aggregate. Generally, palm kernel shell consists of 60 – 90% of particles in the range of 5 – 12.7mm (Okafor, 1988). The specific gravity of palm kernel shell varies between 1.17 and 1.37, while the maximum thickness of the shell was found to be about 4mm (Okpala, 1990).

Figure 1 Palm oil plant plantation

Figure 2 Different sizes of palm kernel shell

The density of palm kernel shell ranges from 1700 to 2050kg/m³ and it depends on factors such as type of sand and palm kernel shell contents (Mohd et al., 2008). Generally, when the density of concrete is lower than 2000kg/m³, it is categorized as light weight concrete. Thus, the palm kernel shell concrete can be produced within this target density of 2000kg/m³, hence palm kernel shell concrete is a light weight concrete. According to (Mohd et al., 2008), the 28 days cube compressive strength obtained was 15 – 25MPa while the structural behavior of palm kernel shell is very limited.

Ndoke (2006) in his work observed the performance of palm kernel shells as partial replacement for coarse aggregate in asphalt cement. According to Teo et al (2006), for structural concrete using oil palm shell (OPS) as light weight aggregate, the compressive strength of OPS concrete was 28.1MPa at 28days curing which is approximately 65% higher than the minimum required strength of 17MPa for structural light weight concrete recommended by American Standard of Testing Materials (ASTM 1330).

Yusuf and Jimoh (2011) worked on the appropriateness of the various nominal mixes of the ‘palm kernel shell concrete’ as rigid pavement. They evaluated the mixes accordingly at both fresh and matured ages with corresponding costs. They reported that the Nigerian PKS satisfies the density criterion for normal concrete and

lightweight concrete in all respects while the palm kernel shell concrete at nominal mixes of 1:1.5:3 and 1:1:2 satisfied the specifications for rigid pavement. In addition, the cost of producing PKS concrete/m² for all levels of traffic and mix proportions is cheaper than those of normal concrete and asphaltic concrete. Saman and Omidreza (2011) reported the influence of oil palm shell on workability and compressive strength of high strength concrete. They noted that the general strength of oil palm shell (OPS) concrete samples produced high strength concrete with compressive strength reaching up to 52.2 N/mm² at 28days.

2. Materials and Methods

2.1 Materials

Ordinary Portland cement was used for the experiment. The cement conforms to BS 12 (1996). The fine aggregate was sourced from a construction site on the University of Ilorin campus, Nigeria. BS 812 (2002) that deals with “Testing Aggregates” was used in carrying out laboratory tests on the aggregates. Palm kernel shells with sizes between 5mm to 16mm were used in different proportions. Tap water from the laboratory was used and was in conformity with BS 3148 (1980).

2.2 Methods

Usually, some oil coating and mud particles stick to the surface of fresh PKS; pretreatment is therefore necessary to remove the impurities. This can be achieved by various methods, including natural weathering, boiling in water and washing with detergent. In this investigation, washing with detergent was adopted. After washing, thorough rinsing was done in order to ensure that all particles of detergent were removed as these can lower the cement performance. The PKS was air-dried and then stock piled. Due to the high water absorption of PKS, pre-soaking of the aggregate for about 45min to 1 hour is necessary. Before the PKS was used as aggregate, it was sieved and only aggregates passing through 16.5mm sieve and retained on the 5mm were used. Particles outside this range have large relative surface areas and high absorption rate. Four levels of concrete were adopted using various size ranges at various percentage as follows:

Sample A (5 – 15 mm) 100%

Sample B (5 – 10 mm) 100%

Sample C (0 – 5 mm) 40% + (10 – 15 mm) 60%
Sample D (5 – 10 mm) 70% + (10 – 15 mm) 30%

2.3 Laboratory Tests

These include the determination of the properties of the PKS and the PKS concrete. The tests carried out include the following: gradation test/sieve analysis, specific gravity, water absorption capacity and moisture content, bulk density, impact value test, slump test, compressive strength test, flexural strength/modulus of rupture test and splitting tensile strength test.

2.4 Production of PKS Concrete Elements

2.4.1 Production of Concrete Cubes

Cement, PKS and sand were used in producing concrete in moulds with dimensions of 150x150x150mm. The nominal mixes used for the production were 1:1½:3 and 1:2:4. A constant water-cement ratio of 0.38 was used for the two mixes. The batching of the mixes was by weight. Plate 1 shows some PKS concrete cubes while Plate 2 shows the set up for Impact Test on concrete.

Plate 1 Cast PKS concrete

Plate 2 Impact test apparatus

2.4.2 Production of Concrete Beams

Concrete beams were cast for the same nominal mixes as given in section 2.4.1. The dimensions of the moulds used were 10 x 10x 50cm. The beam test is useful for the measure of flexural strength of concrete, though used as an indirect method.

2.4.3 Production of Concrete Cylinder

Cylindrically shaped beams were cast for the same nominal mixes of section 2.4.1. The cylindrical test specimens have a height equal to twice the diameter. They were 15cm diameter and 30cm high. Smaller test specimens may be used but a ratio of diameter of the specimen to maximum size of aggregate, not less than 3 to 1 should be maintained.

3. Results and Discussion

The gradation of PKS is given by sieve analysis. This was done by passing PKS through a set of standard sieves and cumulative passing percentages were calculated. The total of about 96% of the PKS used as coarse aggregate passed through sieve 16mm but retained on 5mm. This conformed with literature, hence PKS are classified as coarse aggregate (BS 882, 2002). Grading of coarse aggregate is necessary in order to get a cohesive and light weight concrete. The effects of PKS sizes and proportions on concrete were observed based on the four level of concrete adopted (SAMPLES A - D).

The slump test is a means of assessing the consistency and cohesiveness of fresh concrete. It is used, indirectly, as a means of checking that the adequate amount of water has been added to the mix. The slump test results obtained from the mix design were in range of 4 – 10 mm as shown in Figure 3 Indicating that the concrete has good workability.

Figures 4, 5 and 6 revealed the gradual increase in densities and compressive strengths for the four levels of concrete (Samples A-D). The gradual increase can be attributed to good compaction of concrete with less voids and good curing method. Sample A that contains 100% of Palm kernel shells in the range of (5 – 15 mm) gave the maximum values of densities and compressive strengths respectively.

Figure 3 Slump values for different levels of PKS in light weight concrete.

Figure 4 Densities of PKSC at 28 days

Even though concrete is not expected to resist direct tension, the knowledge of tensile strength is necessary so as to know the load at which the concrete members will crack. Both Flexural Strength and Splitting tests as shown in Table 1 followed the trend of compressive strengths. This will help in our judgment the load that concrete can successfully carry without crack or bend.

Figure 5 Compressive strengths of PKSC (N/mm²) at 28 days

Figure 6 Compressive strengths of PKSC (N/mm²) at 28 days

Table 1 Flexural and splitting test strengths of PKSC (N/mm²)

Sample	Mix ratio 1:1.5:3		Mix ratio 1:2:4	
	Flexural Strength	Splitting Test	Flexural Strength	Splitting Test
Sample A	2.4	1.4	2	1.1
Sample B	2	1.2	1.2	0.8
Sample C	1.65	1.15	1	0.7
Sample D	1.5	1.05	0.8	0.5

4.0 Conclusion

The nominal mix of 1:1.5:3 at 28 days curing gave compressive strength of 20N/mm². The British Code CP 110: 1972 lays the

minimum strength of concrete for reinforced concrete with light weight aggregate as 15MPa and 20MPa for the one with normal aggregate, with mix ratio of 1:1.5:3. Sample A is adequate and satisfied the conditions of being classified as light weight aggregate based on its density and compressive strength. The other Samples (B, C and D) can be used for plain concrete because the minimum strength in those cases was 7MPa. It is worth noting that concrete made with nominal mixes of 1:3:6 and 1:4:8 generally gave poor results.

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